

Isolation and Identification of Non-dermatophytic Fungi from Soil Samples of Owerri Correctional Center, Southeast, Nigeria.

Echeta M. O^{1*}., Igiri V. C¹., Korie M. C²., Ochia A. M²., Nzeagwu M. O².,
Mbanu G. E¹

¹Department of Biological Sciences, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria.

²Department of Biology/Microbiology, Imo State Polytechnic, Omuma, Imo State, Nigeria.

* Corresponding author's email: ogedesecheta@gmail.com

Received: October 25, 2023; Accepted: December 31, 2023 ; Published: March 17, 2024

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10827500

Abstract: Soil is the main abode for pathogenic and non- pathogenic fungi which can serve as causal agents for different cutaneous fungal infections in humans. This study aimed at the isolation and identification of non-dermatophytic pathogenic fungi from the soil of correctional Center in Owerri, Imo State, Southeast Nigeria. Ten soil samples were collected from different points of the Correctional Center. One gram (1g) of the soils were mixed with 9ml of sterile physiologic saline and diluted serially ten-fold. 0.1 ml of the 10⁴ suspension was added to Sabouraud's dextrose agar medium containing chloramphenicol (0.05mg/ml) without cycloheximide and incubated at 30°C for 2-3 weeks, examined daily for fungal growth. Suspected fungal colonies were sub-cultured on fresh SDA to get pure cultures which were used for definitive identification. Six fungal species were found in the soils. *Fusarium solani* was the highest with 50% while all the others such as *Candida* spp. *Candida tropicalis*, *Purpureocillium lilacinum*, *Pseudallescheria boydii* and *Trichoderma harzianum* had the frequency of occurrence of 8.3% each. *Fusarium solani*, *Candida* spp, *Candida tropicalis*, *Purpureocillium lilacinum*, *Pseudallescheria boydii* and *Trichoderma harzianum* were isolated from the soils of the Correctional Centre. They were also found to have caused cutaneous infections among the prison inmates. This result contribute towards a better understanding of the existence pattern of soil-borne non-dermatophytic fungi in the prison and can be useful in the control of public health surveillance of soil-borne fungal pathogens.

Keywords: Non-dermatophytic fungi, soil, Correctional Center, inmates, Imo State.

Introduction

The soil is one of the most complex habitats for microorganisms. It is the main habitat for pathogenic and non-pathogenic microorganisms of which fungi is one of them. Some

environmental factors such as rainfall, heat, organic matter play important roles in the growth of fungi. Some soil-borne fungi serve as causal agents for different degrees of cutaneous fungal infections in humans and animals. Keratinophilic

fungi including the dermatophytes and non-dermatophytes are found in the soil (Deshmukh and Verrek, 2006). According to Seyed *et al.* (2012), keratinophilic dermatophytes and non-dermatophytes which are found in the soil make the soil a source of infection for humans and animals. These fungi are normally distributed in the soil containing creatine and keratin (Pahare *et al.*, 2018). Fungal infections mainly originate from an external source in the environment and can be acquired through direct contact, inhalation, ingestion or traumatic implantation (Hawksworth *et al.* 1977; Richardson *et al.*, 2012). The opportunists such as *Aspergillus* spp. and *Fusarium* spp., mainly found in soils, occur subsequent to trauma and cause mycotic diseases. In the past some researchers have focused on the prevalence of dermatophytes and non-dermatophytes in soil samples (Oyeka and Okoli, 2003; Shokohi, *et al.* (2005); Moallaei *et al.* (2006); Farid and Nareen, 2012; Keyvan, *et al.* (2013); Raja, *et al.* (2017).

Information on the prevalence of dermatophytes and non-dermatophytic fungi in the soils in Nigeria is limited to reports by Oyeka and Okoli, (2003); Gugnani *et al.* (2012); Eze *et al.* (2019). There is no report on isolation of non-dermatophytes from soil of the Correctional Center of Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. Thus it was so considered and of

utmost importance to evaluate the occurrence of non-dermatophytic fungi in soils from different locations of the Correctional Center of Owerri, Imo State Nigeria. This would help us to know the distribution and occurrence of non-dermatophytic fungi in the soil and the risk it posed to the inmates.

Materials and Method

Study Area

The study site was Owerri Correctional Center, Imo State, Southeast, Nigeria. Owerri Correctional Center is located in the Owerri municipal along Owerri-Okigwe Road and close to the Government House. Owerri is in the latitude and longitude coordinates of 5.478310 and 7.025853 respectively. It is the capital city of Imo State, situated near the Otamiri River.

Collection and Processing of Samples.

The soil samples from ten points of the prison yard were collected in sterile specimen bottles and taken to the laboratory for fungal isolation.

Screening of soil samples from the prison yard for the causal agents.

The fungal populations in soil were enumerated on Sabouraud's dextrose agar medium according to the method of Saremi (2005). One gramme (1g) of each sample was diluted with 9ml of normal saline serially and 0.1ml aliquots of soil suspension were spread uniformly with

sterile glass spreader on plates of Sabouraud's dextrose agar (SDA) containing chloramphenicol (0.05mg/ml), which was prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions. All inoculated plates were incubated aerobically at inverted position for 72 hours at 30°C. The plates were examined daily for any fungal growth. Plates suspected of fungal colonies were subcultured on fresh SDA to get pure cultures. Microslide culture technique was carried out on the pure cultures for microscopical examination of fungal cultures before the definitive identification. This is to study the intact fruiting fungus as well as spore formation. Mold isolates were identified by examining their colonial macroscopic and microscopic characteristics. Texture, rate of growth, topography and pigmentation of the front and the reverse side of the culture would be used for their macroscopic identification. Microscopic identification of mold isolates was performed by gently lifting the cover slip from the agar block of the microslide culture technique and

transferring to a few drops of lactophenol cotton blue on a clean glass slide. Color Atlas of Microbiology by Luis *et al*, (1997) and Descriptions of Medical Fungi by David *et al*, (2007) were used for microscopic and macroscopic identification of fungal isolates before definitive identification by molecular studies.

Results and Discussion

Fungal Species in the Soil of Correctional Centre.

The soil samples from the prison yard were analyzed. Table 1 highlights the fungal species found in soil samples collected from ten points in the Correctional Centre. *Fusarium solani* was the highest occurring fungus with 50% while all the other isolate such as *Aspergillus flavus*, *Candida* spp, *Candida tropicalis*, *Purporocilium. lilacinum*, *Pseudallescheria. boydii* and *Trichoderma harzianum* had the frequency of occurrence of 8.3% each as seen in Table 1. Table 2 shows the colonial morphology of the non-dermatophytic fungal isolates from the soil.

Table 1: The Frequency of isolation of Fungal Pathogens obtained from the soil from ten points of the prison yard.

Soil Samples Fungi Species	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	Total N(%)
	N(%)										
<i>A. flavus</i>	-	-	1(50)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1(8.3)
<i>C. tropicalis</i>	1(50)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1(8.3)
<i>C. spp</i>	-	1(100)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1(8.3)
<i>F. solani</i>	1(50)	-	1(50)	1(100)	-	1(100)	1(100)	-	1(50)	-	6(50)
<i>P. boydii</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1(50)	-	1(8.3)
<i>P. lilacinum</i>	-	-	-	-	1(100)	-	-	-	-	-	1(8.3)
<i>T. harzianum</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1(100)	-	-	1(8.3)
Total	2(100)	1(100)	2(100)	1(100)	1(100)	1(100)	1(100)	1(100)	2(100)	0(0.0)	12(100)

A. flavus=*Aspergillus flavus*, *A. sydowii*= *Aspergillus sydowii*, *A. tamarii*= *Aspergillus tamarii*, *C. tropicalis*=*Candida tropicalis*, *C. parasilosis*=*Candida parasilosis*, *C. orthopsilosis*=*Candida orthopsilosis*, *C. spp*= *Candida* species, *C. haemulonis* = *Candida haemulonis*, *F. solani* = *Fusarium solani*. *Paecilomyces* = *Paecilomyces dactylethromorp*, *P. boydii* = *Pseudallescheria boydii*, *P. lilacinum* = *Purpureocillium lilacinum*, *T. harzianum* = *Trichoderma harzianum*. *T. lixii*=*Trichoderma lixi*

Table 2: The Colony Morphology of different Species of Fungi Isolated from Soil Samples from the Correctional Centre.

Isolates	Macroscopic Morphology	Macroscopic Characteristics
<i>A. flavus</i>	<p data-bbox="970 745 1369 884">The conidia heads have uniserate and biserate rows of phialides that cover the entire vesicle.</p>	
<i>C. tropicalis</i>	<p data-bbox="970 1254 1369 1361">Spherical to subspherical budding yeast-like cells or blastoconidia.</p>	
<i>C. spp</i>	<p data-bbox="432 1668 863 1697">Smooth brownish pasty colonies.</p>	

<p><i>F. solani</i></p>	<p>Microscopic feature of <i>Fusarium solani</i> conidia on lactophenol cotton blue.</p>	
<p><i>P. boydii</i></p>	<p>Terminal hyaline conidia, club shaped or cylindrical.</p>	
<p><i>P.dacthyle thromorp</i></p>	<p>The phialides bend away from the axis of the conidiophores, elongated and tapered.</p>	

<p><i>P.</i> <i>lilacinum</i></p>	<p><i>Purpureocilium lilacinum</i> with densely clustered phialides bearing long divergent chains of hyaline to pigmented, smooth or rough, sub-spherical to oval single-celled conidia on lactophenol cotton blue.</p>	
---------------------------------------	--	--

The soil samples from the Correctional Centre were analysed. Mixed culture of *Fusarium solani* and *Candida tropicalis* were found in soil sample A. Soil sample B yielded *Candida* species. Sample C yielded a mixed culture of *F. solani* and *Aspergillus flavus*. *Fusarium solani* was also found in soil samples D, F, G and J. Soil sample E yielded *Purpureocilium lilacinum*. Soil sample H has *Trichoderma harzianum*. *Pseudallescheria boydii* was found in soil sample I. *Fusarium solani* has the highest occurrence in the soil samples analysed. This result is in line with the result of Saremi *et al*, (2011) who reported *Fusarium solani* as the dominant species found in the soil studied. The result is also in agreement with the result of Oyeka *et al*, (2003); Silvestro *et al*, (2013) who isolated

Fusarium species from soil samples. *Aspergillus* spp. is a large group of common saprophytic moulds, and often isolated from soil, air, and plant materials. This group of fungi is normally considered as common contaminants in immunosuppressed patients. The presence of these pathogens in the soil may therefore play a role in the spread and persistence of fungal skin infections among humans and animals. Also the possibility that some of these molds are categorized as true pathogens cannot be underestimated. This is also in concordance with other published works by Jain *et al*, (2011) who analyzed the current status of *Fusarium* infection in animal and human and concluded that this filamentous fungus is widely distributed in the soil and on plants and can cause superficial infections especially on compromised host. In

another study by Bakheshwain *et al*, (2011) they also observed that most mold flora are known to cause superficial or cutaneous infections due to their ability to utilize keratin. The findings of this study is compatible with Tosti *et al*, (2000) who revealed that non-dermatophytes are filamentous fungi which are commonly found in nature as soil saprophytes and plant pathogens. This study also agrees with Ganiae *et al*, (2010); Gugnani *et al*, (2012) who revealed the presence of *Aspergillus* species, *Fusarium* species *Candida* species, and *Trichoderma* species from soil samples. It is also in line with Nwadiaro *et al*, (2015) who isolated *Trichoderma* species from landfill. The result also compares favorably with Moallaci *et al*, (2006) who revealed *Aspergillus* spp as the second most commonly isolated mold from soil samples. The results also compare favorably with Farid *et al*, (2012); Mohsen *et al*, (2017) who revealed that *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, *Penicillium* species were recovered from soil samples.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Fusarium solani, *Candida* spp, *Candida tropicalis*, *Purpureocillium lilacinum*, *Pseudallescheria boydii* and *Trichoderma harzianum* were isolated from the soils of the Correctional Centre. They were also found to have caused

cutaneous infections among the prison inmates. This result contribute towards a better understanding of the existence pattern of soil-borne non-dermatophytic fungi in the prison and can be useful in the control of public health surveillance of soil-borne fungal pathogens. It is recommended that the prison yard or ground should be tiled to reduce contact of the inmates with the soil-borne fungi.

References

- Bakheshwain, S. Khizzi, N. Al-Rasheed, A.M. Al-Ajlan, H.H. and Parvez, S. (2011). Isolation of opportunistic fungi from Dermatophytic samples. *Asian Journal of Dermatology*,3:13-19.
- David, E., Stephen, D. Helen, A. Rosemary, H. and Robyn, B. (2007). Descriptions of Medical Fungi. 2nd edition. Mycology Unit. Women's and children's hospital school of molecular & biomedical science university of Adelaide Adelaide, Australia. 233-256.
- Deshmukh, S.K. and Verekar, S.A. (2006). The occurrence of dermatophytes and other keratinophilic fungi from the soils of Himachal Pradesh (India). *Czech mycology* 58(1-2):117 122.
- Eze, E.M., Ezebialu, C.U. Unegbu, V.N. and Nneji, I.R. (2019). Prevalence of keratinophilic fungi and other dermatophytes from soils of Nnewi in Anambra state, Nigeria. *Novel Research in Microbiology Journal*; 3(3): 379-386
- Farid, M.T., Nareen Q. and Faqi A. (2012). Isolation, Identification and Seasonal Distribution of soil

- borne fungi in different areas of Erbil Governorate. *Journal of Advanced Laboratory Research in biology* 3(4):246-255.
- Ganaie, M.A. Sood, S. Rizvi and Khan, T.A. (2010). Isolation and Identification of Keratinophilic fungi from soil samples in Jhansi City. India. *Plant Pathology Journal*, 9:194-197.
- Gugnani, H. C. Sharma, S. Gupta, B., and Gaddam, S. (2012). Prevalence of keratinophilic fungi in soils of St. Kitts and Nevis. *Journal of Infectious Diseases*; 6(4):347-351..
- Hawksworth, D.L., Rossman, A.Y., (1977). Where are all the undescribed fungi? *Phytopathology*, 1997, Vol. 87(9), pp. 888-891.
- Jain, P.K. Gupta, V.K. Misra, A.K. Gaur, R. Bajpai, V. and Issar, S. (2011). Current status of *Fusarium* infection in Human and Animal. *Asian Journal of animal and verterinary Advances*. 6(3):201-227.
- Keyvan, P., Moosa, R., Kamiar, Z., Ali, R., G., K., (2013). Isolation and molecular identification of keratinophilic fungi from public parks soil in Shiraz, Iran. *Biomedical Research International* 2013:619576.
- Luis, M.M. Marie, T.P, and Ellen, B. (1997). A color Atlas of Diagnostic Microbiology, MosbyYear Book Inc. 19-144.
- Mohsen, N., Parivash K., Reza K., Mahin S., Sassan, R., Mohammad A. A., Hossein, J., (2017). Isolation and Identification of Non-pathogenic and Pathogenic Fungi from the Soil of Greater Tunb, Abu-Musa and Sirri Islands, Persian Gulf, Iran *Journal of Applied Biotechnology Reports*, 4(4),7; 713-718
- Moallaei, H. Ziani, F Pihet, M. Mahmoud, M and Hashemi, J. (2006). Isolation of Keratinophilic Fungi from Soil Samples of Forest and Farm Yards. *Iranian Journal of Public Health*. 35(4):62-69.
- Nwadiaro, P. Ogbonna, A. Wuyep, P. and Adekojo, D. (2015). Keratinophilic activity of *Cladosporium* and *Trichoderma* species isolated from barbers landfill. *International Journal of Biosciences*, 6(10):104-115.
- Oyeka, C.A and Okoli, I (2003). Isolation of dermatophytes and non-dermatophytic fungi from soil in Nigeria. Blackwell Publishing Ltd • *Mycoses*, 46, 318–320.
- Pahare, S., Kamalesh Shukla and Shukla RV. (2018). Keratinophilic fungi from warm, moist, cattle-house of Bilaspur Central-India. *Journal of Microbiology and experimentation* 6(2):46-48.
- Rajah, M., Praveena, G. and William John, S. (2017). Isolation and Identification of fungi from soil in Loyola college campus, Chennai, India. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences* 6(2): 1789-1795.
- Richardson, M.D., Warnock, D.W., (2012). Fungal infection: diagnosis and management. John Wiley & Sons.
- Saremi, H. (2005). *Fusarium*, biology, ecology and taxonomy. Jihad Daneshgahi, Ferdossy Mashhad University, Iran, p.152.

- Saremi, H. Okhovvat, S.M. and Ashrafi, S.J. (2011). *Fusarium* diseases as the main soil borne fungal pathogen on plants and their control management with soil solarization in Iran. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 10(80):18391-18398,
- Seyed Amir Yazdanparast, Hussein Dargahi, Saeed Shahrokhi and Roya Horabad Farahani(2012). Isolation and Investigation of keratinophilic fungi in the parks of municipality distinct of Tehran.*Thrita 2(3):2-5.*
- Silvestro, L. B. Stenglein, S. A., Forjan, H. Dinolfo, M. I. Arambarri, A. M. Manso, L. and Moreno , M. V. (2013). Occurrence and distribution of soil *Fusarium* species under wheat crop in zero tillage. *Spanish Journal of Agricultural Research*,11(1), 72-79.
- Shokohi, T., Hedayati, M.T. and Bakhshi,H.(2005).Isolation of fungi and aerobic actinomycetes from surface soil in Sari. *Journal of Kermanshah Universityof medical sciences* 8:25-32.
- Tosti, A. Piraccini B.M. and Lorenzi S. (2000). Onychomycosis caused by non-dermatophytic molds. *Journal of American Academic of Dermatology*; 42:217-24.